

Consequences of $P = NP$ for Subset Construction

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ABSTRACT

In this short paper we give the notion of the equivalence of the complexity classes due to the recent research according to Rabin-Scott subset construction.

INTRODUCTION

For the past decade the “P versus NP” problem was well studied with conformance that P is a subset of NP. If this happens, then there’s a set of problems which are strictly in NP and not in P assuming $P \neq NP$.

PROOF

We prove the above fact by the assumption already given in the statement before: thus, as we know any non-deterministic finite automata (NFA) can be converted to analogous deterministic finite automata (DFA).

According to our latest research the subset construction is P-complete and, thus, there exist no automata with the strict property given above, thus, it follows that $P = NP$.

CONCLUSION

The common misinterpretation of the “P versus NP” theorem lies between the fact that it can be solved effectively, still, it doesn’t follow that from this consequence we can devise the relationship between two classes.

REFERENCES

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